

DESIGNING NEW MODULE IN CHEMICAL ENGINEERING USING CDIO: GENERAL APPROACH

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Abstract

The CDIO Initiative (www.cdio.org) is an innovative educational framework for producing the next generation of engineers. Throughout the world, collaborators have adopted CDIO as the framework of their curricular planning and continual improvement of their educational programs. In SP, the DCHE Course Management Team (CMT) had used the 12 CDIO Standards in a self-evaluation process aim at identifying areas of improvement in the curriculum.

This paper is the first part of a 2-part submission for ISATE2014 in which we outline and present a general approach used by the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) of Singapore Polytechnic (SP) to designing a new module using the CDIO approach. It built on our earlier effort in aligning the 12 CDIO Standards to SP's existing Academic Quality Management System (AQMS), which is based on the same Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) principles of ISO9001. We used the CDIO Standards for a self-evaluation process aimed that identifying key areas of improvement in the DCHE curriculum. In this paper, we argued that that there are much similarities between the goal of CDIO Framework for re-designing curriculum, which is to "conceive, design, implement, and operate complex value-added engineering systems in a modern team-based engineering environment to create systems and products" and that of introducing a new module into the curriculum; in this case, with the new module being a "product". We showed how Part 4 of the CDIO syllabus corresponded with different stages of module design and development, delivery and evaluation in the AQMS. We henceforth suggested that one can also use the Standards for module-level development work, specifically in designing a new module. We offered our interpretation of the 12 CDIO Standards in the context of new module design and development; which can serve as a checklist to guide a lecturer in the process. An added feature is that our approach can also help the lecturer in pinpointing the right skills and competency needed to deliver the module he/she prepared. A separate paper (second part of this 2-

part submission) will demonstrate the application of the above approach with a case study.

Keywords: *CDIO, module design, continual improvement, chemical engineering*

Introduction

The CDIO Initiative (www.cdio.org) is an innovative educational framework for producing the next generation of engineers. The framework provides students with an education stressing engineering fundamentals set in the context of Conceiving, Designing, Implementing, Operating real-world systems and products. Throughout the world, CDIO Initiative collaborators have adopted CDIO as the framework of their curricular planning and outcome-based assessment, which is based on a 4-part CDIO Syllabus and 12 CDIO Standards.

CDIO provides a comprehensive and detailed codification of the goals of engineering education, with particular emphasis on various engineering skills such as teamwork, communication, critical and creative thinking etc. The main role of the 12 CDIO Standards is to serve as tool for program adoption, evaluation, and continual improvement. The 12 CDIO Standards:

- Define the distinguishing features of a CDIO program;
- Serve as guidelines for educational program reform and evaluation;
- Create benchmarks and goals with worldwide application; and
- Provide a framework for continuous improvement.

In a nutshell, the 12 CDIO Standards address program philosophy (Standard 1), curriculum development (Standards 2, 3 and 4), design-build experiences and workspaces (Standards 5 and 6), new methods of teaching and learning (Standards 7 and 8), faculty development (Standards 9 and 10), and assessment and evaluation (Standards 11 and 12).

In Singapore Polytechnic (SP), the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) adopted CDIO in 2006 as the basis to revamp its curriculum. Over the years, various CDIO skills such as teamwork and communication, personal skills and attitudes (e.g.

critical and creative thinking, managing learning, holding multiple perspectives) have been integrated into the curriculum. Skills relating to conceiving, designing, implementing and operating a process, product or system using relevant principles had also been introduced (Cheah, Phua & Ng, 2013). As part of the effort to continually improving the DCHE curriculum, we have also used the 12 CDIO Standards to carry out self-evaluation of our diploma identify areas of improvement (Cheah, Koh & Ng, 2013).

We now take the process one step further in using the very same standards to guide us in our design of the new modules. This paper covers the effort by the DCHE Course Management Team (CMT) in using the CDIO framework to formulate an approach whereby the 12 standards can serve as a checklist for a lecturer who had been tasked to design and develop a new module, as well as an aid in identifying his/her training needs in delivering the new module that he/she developed.

CDIO Standards and Quality Management

SP's generic product is education and training, which in turn translates into the different diploma courses that it offers to its students. A "course" is defined as a "series of planned learning experiences in a field of study that is integrated and made coherent by a common set of aims". A course is composed of many modules; which is defined as the "basic unit or component of courses offered by the school" with its own set of aims, intended learning outcomes, instructional strategies and assessment scheme. A course is made up of 34-38 modules offered over a period of 3 years, comprising a mix of mostly course-specific modules (core and electives), basic mathematics and sciences, and institutional modules.

The relevance of any diploma course in SP is governed by the Academic Quality Management System (AQMS), which is based on the same Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) principles of ISO9001. The AQMS is shown in Figure 1.

Also shown in Figure 1 is the Staff Development Plan (SDP) which is an important component of lecturer competency building under the People Developer System (PDS). The PDS is a mark conferred by a government agency in Singapore, which, through a certification process, gives recognition to organizations that invest in their people and have a comprehensive system to manage the effective development of their people. Our quality systems, PDS along with its environmental management system are all subjected to external audit by independent assessors.

Cheah, Koh & Ng (2013) had shown that the processes and outcomes of the AQMS and PDS can be mapped directly to the 12 CDIO Standards as shown in Table 1, and henceforth argued that these CDIO Standards can be used to review the diploma (at the course-level) for areas of improvement, to satisfy the requirement of maintaining a quality product, i.e. the DCHE course, under the AQMS.

Figure 1. Relationship of Singapore Polytechnic AQMS Framework and Key Product Realisation Processes Supported by PDS

Table 1. CDIO Standards aligned with AQMS-PDS

SP Framework	Description	CDIO Standard(s) Mapped
AQMS	Need Analysis	1 CDIO as Context
	Curriculum Development System	2 CDIO Syllabus Outcomes
	Outcome: Curriculum	3 Integrated Curriculum 4 Introduction to Engineering 5 Design-Implement Experiences
	Curriculum Delivery System	6 CDIO Workspaces 8 Active Learning
	Outcome: Student Learning	7 Integrated Learning Experiences
	Assessment System	11 CDIO Skills Assessment
	Outcome: Student Performance	
	Evaluation System	12 CDIO Program Evaluation
PDS	Capability Building	9 Enhancement of Faculty CDIO Skills
		10 Enhancement of Faculty Teaching

		Competence
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Module Design and Development in SP

The process shown in Figure 1 at the course level can also be used at the module level. For example, instead of analysing the needs for a new course to serve a particular industry, we use the same system to analyse new developments or changes in the industry to ascertain if there is a need for new knowledge or skills that the industry requires. This can be achieved via several mechanisms, including for example via Advisory Panel, industry focus group discussion, or industry survey. When a need is confirmed, a new module is then developed, and is added to the basket of modules in the existing curriculum after its approval by the relevant authorities consistent with the institutional guidelines. During the module development process, the module coordinator also discusses with his/her reporting officer any training needs and submits the training plan as part of his/her SDP.

After the new module is introduced into the curriculum, it is subjected to the same monitoring and tracking process as other existing modules. Special interest is usually placed on this module in terms of its feedback from students as well as the module coordinator. Module evaluation will be covered in later section.

Correspondence with C-D-I-O

In this paper we use the term “C-D-I-O” to refer to the process of conceiving, designing, implementing and operating a product or systems; to distinguish it from the broader term of “CDIO” skills which is taken to mean competencies in communication, teamwork, critical and creative thinking, etc. When we compare the C-D-I-O process with the module design and development process, we can see close correspondence between the two. Likewise, Lynch et al (2007) compared the CDIO Standards against a number of contemporary theories of teaching and learning such as constructivism and problem-based learning, and concluded that the CDIO approach correlates well with these educational paradigms.

Table 2 compares and contrasts between Sections 4.3 to 4.6 of Part 4 of the SP-customized CDIO syllabus “Conceiving, Designing, Implementing and Operating Systems in the Enterprise and Societal Context” which is most relevant to this work and that of module design and development typical in any curriculum work.

Module-level Design and Development using CDIO Standards - General Approach

With the close matching between module design and development and C-D-I-O; we henceforth propose that we can use the same CDIO Standards to assist the lecturer in designing a new module. This should not be surprising, since a course is made up of many modules, arranged in a proper sequence to deliver the desired

graduate attributes articulated by an education institution. The existing 12 CDIO Standards initially formulated for course-level evaluation is shown in Table 3. Figure 2 shows the application of the CDIO Standards at both course-level and module-level. As mentioned previously, the former had been covered elsewhere and the latter is the focus of this paper.

Table 2. Correspondence between C-D-I-O processes and module design and development

Stage	Relevant Section of SP-CDIO Syllabus	Module Design and Development
CONCEIVE	Identify market needs and opportunities Define Function, Concept and Architecture Model System to Verify Goals Develop Project plan	Need analysis (from environmental scans) Develop module aims Prepare learning outcomes Identify module needs (equipment, facility, etc)
DESIGN	Formulate the Design Plan the Design Process and Approaches Apply Disciplinary Knowledge and Skills Evaluate design/prototype to achieve multiple objectives	Formulate module structure (L:T:P) and assessment types Draft module syllabus Prepare proposal for management approval Prepare Design integrated learning tasks
IMPLEMENT	Plant the Implementation Process Plan for Hardware Realization Planning for Software Implementing Process Planning for Hardware Software Integration Testing, Verifying, Validating, and Certifying Managing Implementation	Prepare roll-out plan, module materials (lecture notes, tutorial, PPT, assignments, etc) Prepare lab manuals and test run activities / experiments, recurrent budgets Prepare lessons timetable and lab schedule Training for other lecturers who co-teach the module
OPERATE	Planning Training and Operation procedures Managing Operations Supporting the Product Lifecycle	Introduce new module Track student learning (e.g. MST, assignments) Conduct module review, e.g. student feedback Prepare module review report and

		follow-up on action items
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Table 3. The twelve CDIO Standards

CDIO Standard	Brief Description of Standard for a Course
Standard 1 CDIO as Context	Adoption of the principle that product and system lifecycle development and deployment - Conceiving, Designing, Implementing and Operating - are the context for engineering education
Standard 2 CDIO Syllabus Outcomes	Specific, detailed learning outcomes for personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills, consistent with program goals and validated by program stakeholders
Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum	A curriculum designed with mutually supporting disciplinary subjects, with an explicit plan to integrate personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills
Standard 4 Introduction to Engineering	An introductory course that provides the framework for engineering practice in product and system building, and introduces essential personal and interpersonal skills
Standard 5 Design-Implement Experiences	A curriculum that includes two or more design-implement experiences, including one at a basic level and one at an advanced level
Standard 6 CDIO Workspaces	Workspaces and laboratories that support and encourage hands-on learning of product and system building, disciplinary knowledge, and social learning
Standard 7 Integrated Learning Experiences	Integrated learning experiences that lead to the acquisition of disciplinary knowledge, as well as personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills
Standard 8 Active Learning	Teaching and learning based on active experiential learning methods
Standard 9 Enhancement of Faculty CDIO Skills	Actions that enhance faculty competence in personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills
Standard 10 Enhancement of Faculty Teaching Skills	Actions that enhance faculty competence in providing integrated learning experiences, in using active experiential learning methods, and in assessing student learning
Standard 11 CDIO Skills Assessment	Assessment of student learning in personal, interpersonal, and product and system building skills, as well as in disciplinary knowledge
Standard 12 CDIO	A system that evaluates programs against these twelve standards, and provides feedback to students, faculty, and other

Figure 2. Application of CDIO Standards at Course-level (for Self-Evaluation) and Module-level (for new design and development)

With this as starting point, we proceed to interpret the Standards in terms of their applicability in new module design and development. The outcome is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. The CDIO Standards in relation to New Module Design and Development

CDIO Standard	Interpretation in SP DCHE Context for New Module Design and Development
Standard 1 CDIO as Context	The context under which the technical content are presented should be consistent with the overall approach for the course as a whole, i.e. CDIO as the context for engineering education, i.e. based on engineering practice, or simulated real-world learning tasks.
Standard 2 CDIO Syllabus Outcomes	The syllabus for the new module shall capture as intended learning outcomes the requirements from stakeholders, e.g. chemical processing industry; and aligned to DCHE Course Aims, i.e. that they must contribute to the development of the desired graduate attributes.
Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum	The new module must be linked to other existing core DCHE modules in terms of its technical content; as well as incorporating various CDIO skills as appropriate, and pegged at the right level of proficiency.
Standard 4 Introduction to Engineering	This standard is NOT APPLICABLE to new module, as it is already addressed in Year 1 module <i>Introduction to Chemical Engineering</i> which also featured a basic level design-implement experience in the form of a mini-project.
Standard 5 Design-	The new module may contain a mini-project if deemed appropriate, pegged at

Implement Experiences	intermediate level to complement existing offerings.
Standard 6 CDIO Workspaces	A review of the new module shall include any laboratory space requirements to support the above-mentioned design-implement experience as well as additional needs for new equipment along with the necessary operating costs, maintenance needs, etc. This may include virtual space including simulation softwares.
Standard 7 Integrated Learning Experiences	This is not restricted to lab-based activities, but all other forms of learning tasks such as out-of-classroom assignments, homework, especially for a new module without a laboratory component. It include the use of e-learning to support student learning.
Standard 8 Active Learning	The new module should include active and experiential learning to support student learning, especially for lecture and tutorial components, more so if it does not have a laboratory component.
Standard 9 Enhancement of Faculty CDIO Skills	The lecturer teaching the module and the teaching team (if applicable) supporting the module must be familiar with teaching and assessing using the CDIO approach, as mentioned in the Standards.
Standard 10 Enhancement of Faculty Teaching Skills	
Standard 11 CDIO Skills Assessment	The design of assessment components for the new module must be aligned to the intended learning outcomes and various learning tasks.
Standard 12 CDIO Program Evaluation	The new module will be subjected to the same existing review processes. Action items arising from the review will be captured in the existing module review report.

Evaluation of New Module

At the SP-level, it is mandatory that all modules and all lecturers be subjected to module and teaching feedback from students, as part of the AQMS. For module feedback, students were asked the following questions as shown in Table 5; while for teaching feedback, the questions are shown in Table 6. All feedbacks are administered online using the Blackboard course management system. Additional feedback can be obtained via teaching observation of lecturer by his/her reporting officer, and student dialogue session with the School Director.

Feedback obtained from both Teaching Feedback and Module Feedback will be discussed at the CMT. Actionable items from the feedback exercises will be

captured in the module review for proper follow-up by the module coordinator and his/her module team.

Table 5. Questions for Module Feedback

Mandatory Questions	
Q1	This module was well taught.
Q2	The course materials in this module were of high quality.
Q3	The workload in this module was manageable.
Q4	Requirements for completing the assessment tasks in this module were clear.
Q5	The library resources met my needs for this module.
Q6	The online teaching and resources in this module enhanced my learning experience.
Q7	Overall, how would you rate this module?
Q8	What aspects of your module were most in need of improvement?
Q9	What were the best aspects of your module?
Additional questions on tutorials and workshops	
Q10	The tutorials were relevant to the aims of the module.
Q11	The tutorials were well taught.
Q12	The tutorials extended my understanding of the subject matter.
Q13	The workshops were relevant to the aims of the module.
Q14	The workshops offered sufficient opportunity to improve my practice of the subject matter.
Q15	The workshops extended my understanding of the subject matter.

Table 6. Questions for Teaching Feedback

Q1	The lecturer organises the lessons well.
Q2	The lecturer explains and illustrates lessons clearly and makes them easy for me to understand.
Q3	I feel the lecturer knows the subject matter well.
Q4	The lecturer keeps the classroom environment positive for learning (e.g. does not allow sleeping, using the mobile phone, talking unnecessarily, etc.).
Q5	I feel the lecturer is concerned for my learning (e.g. approachable, check our understanding).

In addition, in DCHE, the module coordinator is encouraged, in his/her discretion, to work with Academic Mentor to obtain additional feedback from students, over and above those from student feedback from teaching and student feedback on modules. This usually involves designing module-specific survey questionnaires to explore student learning experience in specific classroom- and/or laboratory-based activities; identifying areas that pose challenges to students, and also obtaining input for areas of improvements. This is often supplemented by focus group discussion with selected student representatives. The outcome of the

module review is captured in the online module review and follow-up actions are then carried out.

Discussions

Although it is desired that all the 12 CDIO Standards be used for self-evaluation at the course-level, not all standards are applicable to individual new module design and development. As mentioned in earlier section, a course (in this case, a diploma) is made of up many modules as its constituents. In the design of a new module, the considerations shown in Figure 3 are typical:

Figure 3. Considerations in new design and development`

Of special note is Standard 1, which requires that the new module be designed in the same context of chemical engineering education as the rest of the modules making up the diploma course; and Standard 2, which mandates the alignment of learning outcomes stipulated in a new module with the desired graduate attributes articulated in the diploma. This is to ensure that the overall learning outcomes of DCHE education is consistent with the requirements of all key stakeholders, most notably the chemical processing industry that the diploma serves.

Standard 4 is somewhat “exclusively” devoted to an “introductory” engineering module, which is met by a core module in Year 1 *Introduction to Chemical Engineering*. As such, it is almost certain that this standard will not be required anymore in design and development of any new module.

Likewise, not all modules in DCHE have a laboratory component. Interpreting Standard 6 strictly in terms of physical workspace will severely limit the applicability of this standard to new module design and development. Here we have widen the scope of this standard to include virtual workspaces, such as those based on dynamic simulation or 3-D plant layout designs. Also noteworthy is Standard 5, which provides for additional design-implement experiences over and above those already covered at the basic-level (in the module *Introduction to Chemical Engineering*) and advanced-level (in the capstone *Final Year Project*).

The rest of the standards are applicable to any new module design and development. The usage is similar to

that of course-level self-evaluation and hence not covered in this paper.

Conclusions

This paper has presented a general approach that a lecturer tasked with designing a new module can take using the 12 CDIO Standards. It builds of the premise that a module can be treated as a product that is subjected to the same process of Conceiving, Designing, Implementing and Operating an engineering product, process or systems in the CDIO Framework. It shares our interpretation of the Standards in terms of module design and development and offers advise on areas that a lecturer should focus on when tasked with coming up with a new module. A separate paper will provide a case study on how this approach is applied (Koh & Cheah, 2014).

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